

Performance of Children in Co-Curricular Activities of Non-Working Mothers: A Study in Imphal West District, Manipur.

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ABSTRACT: Co-curricular activities are defined as the activities that enable to supplement and complement the curricular or main syllabi activities which develop the child mentally, physically, socially, morally and emotionally. The definition of non-working mothers are not engaged in paid employment. The objective of study is to find out co-curricular performance, academic achievement, academic impact, classroom performance, study habit and learning outcomes of children of non-working mothers of elementary level. The survey method was used and data were collected through simple random technique whereas questionnaire, interview and observation method were used as tools. 50 boys and girls each of non-working mothers of Imphal West, district, Manipur were used as sample. Data were analysed through simple percentage method. Findings say that boy child performs better than girl child. Parents should be encouraged and engaged in various co-curricular activities to develop their good physical health, mentality, academic, social skills, emotional control, good characters, ethics, discipline and personality in future and outside world.

Key words- Children, co-curricular activities, Imphal West District, non-working mother

I. INTRODUCTION

Co-curricular activities are defined as the activities that enable to supplement and complement the curricular or main syllabi activities which develop the child mentally, physically, socially, morally and emotionally. The definition of non-working mothers are not engaged in paid employment. It is quite true that non-working mothers are devoted to their families to such an extent that they hardly give time for social needs, or activities. It will not only create a positive environment but also will improve her family life. Motherhood is a stage in women's life when she gives birth to her child. Motherhood confers upon a woman the responsibility of raising a child. At this stage, the life of a female undergoes a complete change of 360 degrees. This process also changes the way in which she is perceived in society and her family.

Raising a child is a big responsibility for any mother whether she is working or not. The females who are full time homemakers, also find it difficult to manage home and kids. It is often perceived that non-working mothers have a relaxed life, as they spend a significant time at home managing their household work and family which is totally wrong. In fact, homemakers have an equally vigorous routine like any other working women. So non-working mothers are also facing stress like working mothers. Marsh & Kleitman (2002) and Guest & Schneider (2003) study found that many co-curricular activities have proven to be beneficial in building and strengthening academic achievement, even if the activities are not obviously related to academic subjects. Galiher (2006) advocates of co-curricular activities that this informal aspect of education has a good deal to contribute to developing good citizens. They claim that such activities enable pupils to communicate adequately, prepare them for economic independence, developing healthy minds in healthy bodies, prepare them for family life and direct their use of leisure time. Wasal and Iqbal (2014) found that arranging various healthy activities help students learn better and and also helps in healthy competitions. Ananya (2017) found that in wholesome, the

overall effect of co-curricular activities on the students' academic performance and personality development is positive.

II. JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

In this century, a tremendously emphasis is being given on co-curricular activities. This study has benefitted many and has been incorporating in the school systems, school administrators, educational policy makers and has also helped the parents. It also makes clear to the students the effect of co-curricular activities, its role in overall personality makeup and developing their good physical health, mentality, academic, social skills, emotional control, good characters, ethics, discipline and personality in future. It also improves children in responsibility taking, life skills and help them evolve as smart citizens of the country.

III. OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

To find out Co-curricular performance of children of uneducated non-working mothers of elementary level

- 3.1 Participation of co-curricular activity
- 3.2 Academic achievement
- 3.3 Academic impact
- 3.4 Classroom performance
- 3.5 Study habit
- 3.6 Learning outcomes

IV. DELIMITATION

- 1.2 Children are from class VI-VIII of Imphal, West District and 50 boys and girls each.
- 1.3 The study delimited the uneducated, non- working mother.

V. METHODOLOGY

The survey method was used and data were collected through simple random technique whereas questionnaire, interview and observation method were used as tools. 50 boys and girls each of non-working mothers of Imphal West, district, Manipur were used as sample. Data were analysed through simple percentage method and bar diagram.

VI. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

Table no. I: Participation of co-curricular activities

Category	Participation of co-curricular activities		
	Good	Average	Poor
BOYS	20%	24%	56%
GIRLS	16%	20%	60%

Table no. 1 revealed that 20% boys and 16% girls found good in participation of co-curricular activity whereas 24% of boys and 20% of girls found in average participation and 56% of boys and 60% of girls found poor participation in co-curricular activity.

Table no. II: Academic achievement of co-curricular activities

Category	Academic Achievement of co-curricular activities		
	Good	Average	Poor
Boys	12%	8%	80%
Girls	8%	4%	88%

Table no. II revealed that 12% of boys and 8% of girls found good academic achievement in co-curricular activity whereas 8% of boys and 4% of girls found average achievement and 80% boys and 88% girls found in poor academic achievement.

Table no. III. Academic impact of co-curricular activities

Category	Academic Impact of co-curricular activities		
	Positive	Negative	Neutral
Boys	24%	40%	36%
Girls	20%	12	8

Table no. III revealed that, 24% boys and 20% girls found positive academic impact of co-curricular activity whereas 40% of boys and 12% girls found negative academic impact and 36% boys and 8% girls found neutral academic impact of co-curricular activity.

Table no. IV. Classroom performance

Category	Classroom performance		
	Good	Average	Below average
Boys	20%	24%	56%
Girls	16%	20%	60%

Table no. IV. Revealed that 20% boys and 16% girls found good classroom performance whereas 24% of boys and 20% girls found average classroom performance and 56% boys and 60% girls found below average classroom performance.

Table no. V. Study habit

Category	Study habit		
	Self interest	Being motivated	Indifferent/Casual
Boys	32%	12%	80%
Girls	8%	4%	88%

Table no. V. revealed that 32% boys and 8% girls found Self interest of study habit whereas 12% of boys and 4% girls found being motivated of study habit and 80% boys and 88% girls found Indifferent/Casual of study habit.

Table no. VI. Learning outcomes

Category	Learning outcomes		
	80%-100%	60%-79%	<59%
Boys	Nil	12%	88%
Girls	Nil	8%	92%

Table no. VI. revealed that no boys and girls found 80%-100% of learning outcomes whereas 12% of boys and 8% girls found 60%- 79% of learning outcomes and 88% boys and 92% girls found 59%- below of learning outcomes.

VII. SUGGESTIONS

- 7.1 Students should be encouraged to engage in various co-curricular activities to develop their total personality for the outside world. This can be done by incorporating such activities in the school time table by the elementary school authorities.
- 7.2 Today there are so many negative ways for children to take and go. If we don't provide more positive alternative activities, there won't be much choice for them. Being involved in co-curricular activities always allows students to show effort to learn team spirit. These abilities and skills of co-curricular activities would be the keys to being successful in everyday life.
- 7.3 Teachers should be instructed to serve as co-ordinators for each co-curricular activity. This will make students attach importance to the activities.
- 7.4 School head masters or teachers should be provided with counselling programs to help parents explain about the benefits of co-curricular activities in the life of students in future.
- 7.5 Parents should be told to encourage their children to participate in co-curricular activities to improve children personality. Different children have different likings and personalities. The involvement in such activities helps them in development in number of ways.
- 7.6 Parents should search out those activities in which their children can participate well according to his or her abilities. They should provide their children with the best available facilities so that they can be able to perform well in both academics and in ground.
- 7.7 Co-curricular activities develop good physical health, mentality, academic, social skills, emotional control, good characters, ethics and discipline.

- 7.8 Binge watching television cannot be regarded as a healthy activity. Parents should motivate their children to choose their co-curricular activity and they should have a check on their activity progress. Parents have an essential role in the development of the character and health of their children.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

- 8.1 Boarder co-curricular activities should be included in syllabus and same value should be counted in academic achievements of children. Teachers, administrators, planners, counsellors and parents should be encouraged children for participation of co-curricular activities.
- 8.2 The present study is limited to one district, Imphal West district in Manipur state. In order to have some broader and comprehensive perspective, study may be extended to more districts or to other states or other countries.
- 8.3 Furthermore, the author has to rely on a small size of sample due to time and cost constraints. It would be better to select more schools and higher secondary schools in the population.
- 8.4 Studies can also be taken up at various levels i.e. school, college and university level.
- 8.5 The study has its implications for teachers and students. Teachers should try to develop sound co-curricular atmosphere in the class rooms as well as in the schools so that the students do not confront with any adjustment problem. They should act as facilitator for the children of non-working mothers so that their loneliness at home is supplemented by empathetic attitude of teachers.

IX. CONCLUSION

Boys are more active than girls and girls are always the shy type for physical activities in front of others. Boys are more compassionate towards co-curricular activities compare with girls because they are more energetic than girls. Boys like more adventures than girls. They are physically more fit and stronger than girls. Most of the co-curricular activities require energy. Majority of the habits that boys have are mostly physical activities.

References

- [1] Acquah, B. Y. S. & Anti Partey, P. (2014). The influence of co-curricular activities on students' performance in economics. *Journal of Educational Management*, 6, 147 – 160.
- [2] Aiswarya, R.(2011). The working mother, a winner all the way, *The Hindus,e-paper*.
- [3] Ananya,S.(2017).Effect of co-curricular activities on academic achievement of students. *International journal education and multidisciplinary studies*,6(3),241-153.
- [4] Broh, B.A. (2002). Linking extracurricular programming to academic achievement: who benefits and why? *Sociology of Education*, 75, 69-96.
- [5] Darling, N., Caldwell, L. L., & Smith, R. (2005). Participation in school-based co-curricular activities and adolescent adjustment. *Journal of Leisure Research*, 37, 51-76.
- [6] Galiher, S. (2006). Understanding the effect of extracurricular involvement. A Research Project Report Presented to the School of Education Indiana University South Bend In Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree Master of Education. Indiana: University South Bend
- [7] Guest, A., & Schneider, B. (2003). Adolescents' extracurricular participation in context: The mediating effects of schools, communities, and identity. *Sociology of Education*,76(2), 89-109.
- [8] https://www.momspresso.com/parenting/article/stress-in-non-working-mothers-and-its-impact-on-mothers-and-its-impact-on-mothers-and-its-impact-on-mother-child-relationship?utm_source.

- [9] Katozai, M. A. (2004). Preparation for the PCS screening Test of Senior English Teacher. University Publishers Shop # 8–A Afghan Market, *Qissa Khwani Peshawar*. pp. 132-135
- [10] Marsh, H. W. & Kleitman, S. (2002). Co-curricular school activities. The good, the bad, and the nonlinear. *Harvard Educational Review* 5, 72.
- [11] Morrissey K,(2005). The relationship between out of school activities and positive youth development: An investigation of the influences of communities and family. *Adolescence*, 40, 67-85.
- [12] Wasal, Kh.& Mohammad, I. (2014). Role of co-curricular activities in school effectiveness. *Middle-East journal of scientific research*, 21(11),2169-2176.